

Supplementary Material

Digital light processing 3D printing of isosorbide- and vanillin-based ester and ester-imine thermosets: Structure-property-recyclability relationships

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This supporting information file contains 7 Figures and 1 Table on 5 pages.

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum of MI monomer.

Figure S2. ^1H NMR spectrum of MV monomer.

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of SB monomer.

Figure S4. Working curves for printing of the different resins.

Figure S5. Stress-strain curves of the printed thermosets.

Figure S6. Stress-strain curves of MI75RP1, MI75RP2 and MI75CR.

Figure S7. Stress-strain curves of MI50RP1 and MI50RP2.

Table S1. Stress strain measurements.

Sample	Elastic modulus [MPa]	Stress at break [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]
MI50	2026 ± 250	47 ± 13	5 ± 1
MI50RP1	624 ± 51	10 ± 1	4 ± 2
MI50RP2	681 ± 52	10 ± 2	3 ± 1
MI75	1925 ± 484	58 ± 9	6 ± 2
MI75RP1	421 ± 134	9 ± 2	6 ± 3
MI75RP2	562 ± 110	6 ± 3	2 ± 1
MI75CR	393 ± 152	11 ± 2	7 ± 1
SB_MI50	1163 ± 215	42 ± 4	7 ± 2
SB_MI50RP1	1088 ± 217	14 ± 6	3 ± 1
SB_MI50RP2	1070 ± 214	10 ± 3	2 ± 1
SB_MI50Mild1	1229 ± 271	15 ± 4	2 ± 0
SB_MI50Mild2	876 ± 62	9 ± 2	3 ± 0
SB_MI50CR	1045 ± 116	21 ± 2	4 ± 1